

THE INHERITANCE OF THE FIBER YIELD TRAIT IN F₁ PLANTS OBTAINED AS A
RESULT OF CROSSBREEDING IN SOME INTRASPECIFIC VARIETIES OF THE
G.HIRSUTUM L.

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Annotation: This article analyzes the inheritance and variability of the fiber yield trait in F₁ plants obtained by hybridization with certain subspecies and cultivated varieties of the species *G.hirsutum* L. The fiber yield in F₁ plants obtained as a result of crossbreeding certain subspecies and cultivated varieties belonging to the species *G.hirsutum* L. is the utmost importance from a breeding perspective.

Key words: Subspecies, variety, hybrid, combination, fiber yield, inheritance, variability, degree of dominance.

Introduction

In cotton cultivation, fiber yield is considered one of the important indicators that determine the type and value of cotton plants. Fiber yield is a complex trait, composed of several constituent elements and closely related to them. In particular, fiber yield depends on the size and weight of the particular, fiber yield depends on the size and weight of the seeds as well as the number and weight of fibers on it, namely the fiber index. This, in turn, is expressed by the number and weight of fibers located on the surface of the seed. Polymorphic intraspecific genetic diversity and forms of the species *G.hirsutum* L. and *G.arboreum* L. have been analyzed through intraspecific and interspecific hybridization, focusing on the most important indicators of valuable economic traits of cotton such as the weight of cotton per boll, the weight of 1000 seeds, fiber length, fiber yield and fiber index. Recombinants have also been selected for breeding research.

H.X.Matniyazova and others [3], H.X.Matniyazova and others [4] emphasized that conducting backcrosses with varieties to combine morpho-biological and basic economic traits in interspecific hybrids is highly effective. Furthermore, it was noted that in the initial hybrids created, the main indicators of productivity - the number of bolls per plant and the weight of cotton per boll - are inherited under the control of polygenic traits, with the dominance of high-performing initial forms, without deviating from the principles of genetics, where dominant traits are expressed in the first generation. In addition, numerous scientists have also conducted research and investigations on yield-related traits. As in all crops, in cotton as well, valuable economic traits, including the main indicators determining fiber quality-such as fiber length, fiber micronaire, and fiber strength-as well as fiber yield, are controlled by quantitative genes.

She noted that the degree of correlative relationship between valuable economic traits of cotton is divided into three groups: the first group includes strongly correlated traits-the weight of cotton per boll and the number of seeds in it; the second group includes moderately correlated traits-fiber yield and fiber index; as well as the third group is composed of weakly correlated traits-fiber length, the weight of 1000 seeds, and the number of unfertilized seeds.

Research object and research. The research was conducted on the experimental farm are belonging to the Department of Selection, Seed Production, and Cultivation of Medicinal Plants of the faculty of Agrobiological of the Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies.

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The research object included the subspecies of cotton *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*mexicanum* var.*microcarpum* f.*palmeri*, *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum*, *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum* var.*gambia*, and the cultivated varieties Genofond-2, Omad and Kelajak.

During the research, the inheritance of fiber length indicators of *G.hirsutum* L. subspecies and cultivated cotton varieties was analyzed.

The degree of dominance of traits in F₁ plants was determined and analyzed according to the S.Wright formula presented in the works of G.E.Beil and R.E.Atkins:

$$hp = \frac{F_1 - MP}{P - MP}$$

hp - Dominance coefficient;

F₁ - The average arithmetic indicator of the hybrid;

MP - The average arithmetic indicator of the trait of both parental forms;

P - The average arithmetic indicator of the trait of the better parent form.

hp = 0 – No dominance;

0 < hp < ±1,0 – Intermediate dominance;

hp = ±1,0 – Complete dominance;

hp > ±1,0 – Over dominance.

Research results: During the research, the inheritance and variability of fiber yield indicators of *G.hirsutum* L. subspecies and cultivated cotton varieties were analyzed.

The average fiber yield value of intraspecific diversity of *G.hirsutum* L. species mainly ranges from 25.6% to 31.4%. The subspecies *G.hirsutum* L. subs. *punctatum* var. *gambia* showed a high fiber yield (31.4%), while the subspecies *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum* exhibited lower values (25.6%). The average fiber yield of cultivated cotton varieties was recorded in the range of 34.8% to 36.7%.

In F₁ plants obtained from reciprocal hybridization of *G.hirsutum* L. subspecies with cultivated varieties, the average fiber yield ranged from 33.6% to 34.2%. In the F₁ hybrid combination *G.hirsutum* L. subs. *punctatum* x "Kelajak" variety, the average fiber yield was 29.7% (variability amplitude 27.6-32.0%), and the inheritance was recorded as incomplete dominance with a dominance coefficient of hp = -0.22. However, in its backcross combination, "Kelajak" variety x *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum*, the average fiber yield was 33.1% (variability amplitude 31.0-35.0%), and the inheritance showed intermediate dominance with a dominance coefficient of hp = 0.42. In the F₁ hybrid combinations of "Omad" variety x *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum* var.*gambia*, the average fiber yield was 35.8% (variability amplitude 31.0-35.0%), and complete dominance was observed with a dominance coefficient of hp=0.60. In its backcross combinations, *G.hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum* var.*gambia* x "Omad" variety, the average fiber yield was 33.8% (variability amplitude 31.0-35.0%), and complete dominance was observed with a dominance coefficient of hp=0.26.

Table-1

Initial sources and the inheritance of the fiber yield trait in F₁ plants

№	Initial forms and F ₁ generation combinations	Fiber yield, %				
		$\bar{x} \pm S$	Limit	S	V %	hp
Initial forms						
1	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i>	26,4±0,68	24,0-28,0	1,5	5,7	-
2	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i>	25,6±1,0	23,0-29,0	2,4	7,4	-
3	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i>	31,4±1,1	28,0-34,0	2,6	8,3	-
4	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>euhiirsutum</i> “Sulton” variety	34,8±0,73	33,0-37,0	1,6	4,2	-
5	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>euhiirsutum</i> “Omad” variety	35,2±0,58	34,0-37,0	1,3	3,7	-
6	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>euhiirsutum</i> “Genofond-2” variety	36,7±1,1	34,0-40,0	2,4	6,3	-
7	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>euhiirsutum</i> “Kelajak” variety	36,2±0,97	34,0-39,0	2,1	5,9	-
F₁ hybrids						
1	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i> x “Kelajak”	34,6±0,87	32,0-37,0	1,9	5,6	0,66
2	“Kelajak” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i>	33,9±1,4	31,0-37,0	3,2	9,6	0,52
3	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i> x “Genofond-2”	32,4±1,5	29,0-37,0	3,4	10,6	0,16
4	“Genofond-2” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i>	35,8±1,2	32,0-38,0	2,6	7,4	0,41
5	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i> x “Omad”	31,9±0,97	29,0-35,0	2,1	6,8	0,25
6	“Omad” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i>	33,2±1,1	30,0-37,0	2,9	7,8	0,55
7	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i> x “Sulton”	34,6±1,0	30,0-37,0	2,6	7,5	0,95
8	“Sulton” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>mexicanum</i> var. <i>microcarpum</i> f. <i>palmeri</i>	33,6±0,92	31,0-36,0	2,0	6,1	0,71
9	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> x “Kelajak” variety	29,7±0,84	27,6-32,0	1,9	6,3	-0,22
10	“Kelajak” variety x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i>	33,1±0,71	31,0-35,0	1,6	4,8	0,42
11	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> x “Genofond-2” variety	34,2±1,2	30,0-37,0	2,6	7,6	0,55
12	“Genofond-2” variety x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i>	34,8±1,5	29,0-37,0	3,3	9,6	0,65
13	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>Punctatum</i> x “Omad” variety	32,7±1,0	29,0-34,0	2,4	7,2	0,48
14	“Omad” variety x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i>	35,2±0,86	33,0-38,0	1,9	5,4	1,0
15	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i> x “Sulton” variety	34,1±1,0	32,0-38,0	2,9	6,6	0,85
16	“Sulton” variety x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i>	35,4±1,1	33,0-39,0	2,5	7,1	1,13
17	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i> x “Kelajak”	34,5±0,68	34,0-37,0	1,5	4,4	0,29
18	“Kelajak” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i>	36,8±1,0	34,0-40,0	2,4	6,5	1,25
19	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>Punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i> x “Genofond-2”	34,2±1,2	30,0-37,0	2,6	7,6	0,04
20	“Genofond-2” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i>	36,7±0,86	34,0-39,0	1,9	5,2	1,0
21	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i> x “Omad”	33,8±0,73	31,0-35,0	1,6	4,9	0,26
22	“Omad” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L.subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i>	35,8±1,2	33,0-39,0	2,7	7,7	0,60
23	<i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i> x “Sulton”	33,9±1,2	30,0-36,0	2,7	7,9	0,47
24	“Sulton” x <i>G.hirsutum</i> L. subs. <i>punctatum</i> var. <i>gambia</i>	35,3±0,98	32,0-38,0	2,2	6,1	1,29

Thus, according to the analysis of the inheritance of fiber yield indicators in F₁ hybrid combinations obtained by hybridizing *G.hirsutum* L. subspecies with cultivated varieties, in the "Omad" variety x *G. hirsutum* L. subs.*punctatum* var.*gambia* hybrid combinations, the average fiber yield was 35.8% (variability amplitude 31.0-35.0%), exhibiting inheritance in a complete dominance state with a dominance coefficient of $h_p=0.60$, indicating positive heterosis. The selected hybrid forms with high fiber yield serve as a valuable initial source for genetic and breeding research.

USED REFERENCES

1. Abdiyev F., Umirov D., Egamberdiyeva S., Muminova B. The current state and development prospects of the selection and seed production sector. // Collection of materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference. Tashkent, 2014th year 18th december. 11-6.
2. Abdiyev F. Creating initial material for practical selection from high-generation hybrids of the *G.barbadense* L. Автореф к/х.ф.н. Tashkent. 2011. Б. 18-19.
3. Matniyazova H.X., Nabiye S.M., Khamidullayev Sh.A. Studying the cotton weight per boll in Prospects for the development of cotton growing in Uzbekistan» (I chapter) Tashkent, 2014. Б-190-192.
4. Matniyazova H.X., Sherimbetov A.G. Variability of the cotton weight per boll trait in another generation of hybrids of *G.hirsutum* L. // Collection of materials from the scientific-practical conference on the topic of «Current problems of biology and ecology». –Tashkent, 2015. Б-135-137
5. Muminov Kh.A. *G.herbaceum* L. ва *G.arboreum* L. Intraspecific and interspecific phylogenetic relationships of cotton species.// Uzbek biological journal.- Tashkent. 2017. - №4.- Б. 41-44.
6. Beil G.E., Atkins R.E. Inheritance of quantitative characters sorgum. // Jow State Journal of Science. 1965. - № 3. - P.35-37.